

A New Robust Real-time Video Streaming Analysis Algorithm for Effective Green Wave Route for Traffic Control Application

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Abstract— Intelligent transportation system (ITS) has important impact in recent years. In today's world traffic jam during peak hour is one of the major concerns and is rapidly increasing in metropolitan cities. In peak hour emergency vehicles (EV) like police cars, fire brigade, ambulance get stuck in traffic due to which they are not able to reach their destination in time resulting in loss of human lives. This paper presents different method and algorithm used to overcome the problem of traffic congestion. Concept of continuously green wave route is focused in this paper where there is smooth flow for the traffic so that it reaches the destination in time and minimizing the delay caused by traffic jam. Shortest path algorithm and density measurement techniques are presented in this paper to provide an intelligent traffic control flow in emergency condition. Our focus is in accuracy, for evaluating different methods of controlling traffic signal and to make a comparison with other intelligent transportation algorithm that have been recently used.

Keywords- Density measurement, Emergency vehicle (EV), Green wave route (GWR), intelligent transportation system (ITS), shortest path, traffic signal control, traffic congestion.

I. INTRODUCTION

As large quantity of vehicles has been increasing rapidly on road over the past few years in urban areas due to which problem like traffic congestion, road accident and other serious related issues occur. The basic reason for this is inefficient setting of traffic signal timing, growing population and everyone's desire to possess their own personal mode of transport [1].

One of the effective measures for dealing with this issue is traffic signal control. In a traffic signal control, the setting of signal time length on need to enable vehicle to pass through many intersections rapidly, thereby saving time and reducing

congestion and fuel usage [2]. With this aim, traffic engineers and scientists are seeking solution to the questions of how the capacity of the road network could be used more efficiently and how operations can be improved by using new technologies [3].

Recently, considerable amount of research is performed in the area of Green intelligent transportation system (GITS). It has received significant importance to solve transportation problems such as congestion, accidents and pollution emissions. So, an efficient traffic signal control is highly important to solve the issue. Green wave mechanism is used for the traffic signal coordination control, which improve the traditional fixed traffic light scheme. A green wave occurs when a series of traffic lights are coordinated to allow uninterrupted traffic flow over various intersection in one main direction. Any vehicle travelling along with the green wave will see sequence of green lights, and not have to stop at intersection. This will reduce higher traffic loads and noise [4].

In this paper we discuss different ways of overcoming traffic congestion on road. One of the techniques is image processing. A video camera is used for capturing images of road and checking traffic density on traffic signal and then applying suitable morphological operation on image to extract vehicles from image and then apply density measurement algorithm so that on signal point where there is more traffic greener signal duration will be increased and set unless the density on that side will become low [5].

As our application is helping to avoid traffic in emergency cases and to give comfort to people in emergency (such as war, earthquake, ambulance and fire brigade). Ambulance is a good example as a person is in serious condition and due to traffic congestion or signal is closed, it takes time to reach

hospital so a sudden death may cause. Many previous researches took place to overcome this kind of problems.

Our main aim is to give Green Wave route to all users which are in emergency and only that users are authorized to apply for Green Wave route. We also provide an application to smart users (such as private vehicles, cab etc.), who wants to see only Green Wave route. Our second aim is to provide navigation system to users and tells them the fastest path as well as alternative way to reach the destination.

This paper provides a complete analysis and comparison of existing method and techniques for traffic management in emergency condition and identifies future research directions. The remaining part of the paper is structured as follows: in section 2, a brief study of related works in recent years. Section 3 comprise of our quantitative and qualitative comparison of our proposed methodology with its algorithm. In section 4, analysis or result of the proposed work are discussed. Finally, section 5 concludes the paper by providing future work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many researches for reducing traffic congestion took place. Green Wave occurs when series of traffic light allow continuous traffic flow over a number of intersections. The vehicle travelling along the green route will see a progressive cascade of green lights and not have to stop at intersections. Green wave route reduces the load of traffic and energy as well. In this section, we introduce research for Green Wave Route (GWR).

Green Swirl is a system which is used to control the traffic signal. It is enabled to give smooth flow of traffic through signals without any stop. In this research TSC (Traffic Signal Control) method is used where Green Wave is formed. In this Green Swirl app manually, swirls are designed according to the road network and city pattern. Vehicles can run at the lawful speed limit on a swirl without stopping unless there is traffic jam. Many swirls of different sizes are formed at the same time. Green Drive is a route guidance system which is used to get shortest path. In this research they also used navigation system to enhance the overall control of the city. In this research DRG (Dynamic Route Guidance) method is used where k-shortest path algorithm is utilizing. In order to reduce traffic congestion formed by unequal traffic DRG is needed to distribute the traffic. Each road segment travel time is calculated by Green Drive and guides the vehicles in order to minimize the travel time for cars around the whole city. [6-8]

ITS Control System is a system which interlinks the ambulance and the traffic signals station using cloud network. It uses the functionality of RFID (radio frequency identification) to implement the ITS control. In this app they provide the proper green wave route for the Ambulance to reach the destination on time in emergency condition. In this system first to register Ambulance to the cloud network. This app work both the RFID and Cloud, if the RFID will not work properly and then the user sends the condition to blocked state. In this way the cloud optimized the signal without the

verification of the RFID. Second if condition is Emergency then the signal is green and third if condition is non-Emergency then the signal is continuous without the optimization. In this Android Application user send the status of the Ambulance and then check the condition and then optimized the signal. This android Application is developed to provide the additional information about the Ambulance and get the current location using GPS (Global Positioning System) system to the server database. GPS installer is installing the mobile they sensed the current location. If condition is Emergency, then the server send the current location and status (condition) to traffic signal controller. Traffic signal controller change the signal after the verification of the RFID reader. The current location is sent to the traffic signal controller through cloud, if RFID reader fail, then driver send a "blocked" command to the cloud network. At this case, traffic signal is cleared without verification based on the server information. In this Android Application there is four buttons (Emergency, Non-Emergency, Blocked and Register) these app send the data to cloud network and cloud can access the both signal controller and database that is created by the system. In database can store the all information about the signal and then they check the status of the Ambulance and match the given database that can store the different type of status. If match the status of the Ambulance then perform the operation and they send the information to cloud, and then cloud send the data to traffic signal controller and they optimize the signal to green. [9-11]

In Real time optimized traffic management algorithm two methods were discussed which is **periodic signal control and Dynamic signal control**. Periodic signal control method is ineffective for real time traffic situation because it functions on a pre-defined series and duration of green light for various lanes. However, this method has limited efficiency. A need of another method Dynamic Traffic signal control Algorithm which works on the following four steps;

- First determine the queue length of traffic.
- See the present scenario (best to worst) as well as determine the presence of Emergency vehicles (ambulance, Fire brigade etc.)
- Give green light to the most suitable line.
- Calculate duration of green light to the given line.

The proposed method solves the problem of giving route to emergency vehicles by setting the priority and give green light to that path [12-14].

In survey paper for Intelligent Traffic Control System instructions are given of the intelligent traffic control system for ambulance. ITS control system is basically giving the green corridor (Green Wave) for ambulance which is stuck in traffic congestion. This is an android application in which they have three modules one is admin second is driver/ambulance and third one is controlling signals. Admin module is responsible for providing the green route. Driver/ambulance is responsible for sending request to reach the destination as well as for permission of green route. Controlling signal is responsible to manipulate the traffic signal and provide the green corridor for ambulance. [15-17]

Providing a clear and open route for emergency vehicle is the first priority in this paper. It also shortens its travel time. A dispatching algorithm assumed only one emergency vehicle per direction. It has following procedure of way going forward:

- The sensor senses that emergency vehicle is arriving. (I.e. police cars, ambulances, fire engines, fire brigade).
- Calculate distance between emergency vehicle and point of intersection.
- Now check that all the emergency vehicles are at the same distance or not. If they are at same distance randomly choose the direction to set the green light. Otherwise choose the direction set in ascending order with the less distance.
- Based on calculated distance values determine green light duration and send these values to the traffic lights.
- Confirm the passage of emergency vehicle and measure the speed of emergency vehicle and count the vehicles moving along with emergency vehicles at the intersection.
- The system sends the measured data to the next intersection.
- Now the controller checks the presence of emergency vehicle. If present, then the algorithm repeats again from step 2 to step 6. Otherwise it resumes normal operation. [18-20]

In novel approach to implement green wave route and detection of stolen vehicles to develop an effective system they are using RFID, Global system for Mobile communication (GSM) modules and latest high-speed microcontrollers to achieve the anticipated result. The main objective is to detect emergency vehicle and track their location to provide them green wave route. For detecting the emergency vehicle, they are using digital image processing. They also work on distorted image due to weather for this they use RFID. [21-23]

In density-based Traffic signal system take an image of a road and perform different techniques of image processing from which number of cars detected. After detecting cars system calculate the density. Raspberry pi is used as a microcontroller which provides the signal timing based on the traffic density. [24-26]

This system used traffic management server (TMS), vehicles, RSUs, sensors deployed at different locations, all interconnected with a VANET system. Finding the priority of the vehicle they can use Prioritizing Emergency Vehicle algorithm. [27-29].

III. PROPOSED METHOD

The proposed solution is to design an application for a user to facilitate him/her in emergency condition.

Our main purpose is to find the fastest path route from the source to the destination and creating a Green Wave route which is signal free.

We are going to develop our system in following modules:

- Module 1: Admin
- Module 2: Controlling signals

In **Figure 1**, Density Measurement of traffic at signal intersection is very important to minimize the delay of traffic congestion so, we measure density using real time video streaming analysis to calculate density on each intersection point. We mark specific location point to each sides of road to that of traffic signal, so that any vehicle come between these coordinates would count as a density as the vehicle increases. Automation of signal can be changed according to calculated density.

Figure 1 Proposed system for density measurement

Density Measurement of traffic at signal intersection is very important to minimize the delay of traffic congestion so we measure density in our application and set signal timing according to density shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1 Green Signal Timing

Threshold Value	Number of Cars	Condition	Signal Timing
4	3	$3 < 4$	5 sec
4	7	$7 > 4$	10 sec
4	12	$12 > 4$	18 sec
4	4	$4 = 4$	8 sec
4	1	$1 < 4$	3 sec

In desktop application we generate a green wave route to cater the emergency condition (i.e. Ambulance, fire Brigade, Police cars, VIP Routes) so that the emergent user reach their destination on time without any loss of human lives. Our way of proceeding the approach is that the server admin is always active for emergency condition (request) and admin change the signal status and generate the green wave route and show that route to emergent user as shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 Green Wave Route

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

A lot of analysis have been carried out on efficient and smart traffic control system, but a more reliable and secure solution for overcoming traffic congestion and catering emergency vehicle is yet to discuss. Therefore, a robust real time video streaming analysis algorithm has been developed to minimize the issue of traffic jam in peak hours and overcome the delay time of emergency vehicles on traffic signal. In this section , performance of our system is evaluated by comaparison with previous proposed works, i.e. Green Drive [1], Green swirl [2] and other system. The different type of methods approach and system performance of existing researches has been mentioned in the following below table. Our propsed simulation scenario has been shown in below **Figure 3** where different type of priority has been sets to minimize the traffic congestion and waiting in time delay in emergency condition. A simple idea has been proposed which can be implemented any where in urban cities to shorter the possible dealy time and death loss in emergency condition that is in ambulance case.

Figure 3 Simulation Scenario

Table 2 Comparison of Existing System with our Proposed System

	Country / University	Existing Method	Proposed Approach	System performance
1.	Army Public College of Management & Sciences University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan	Robust Real-time Video Streaming Analysis Algorithm	We cater the emergency condition and generate green wave route for emergency vehicle (i.e. Ambulance, police, fire brigade). For normal users we calculate density on each side of intersection point and where congestion is more (i.e. high) that signal will open for long time.	Our proposed method reduces the time delay and congestion to almost 5 to 10% , as our main concern is to provide green wave route to emergent users. However Normal users can overcome congestion on the basis of density calculate on each side of intersection point. Our system is 90% accurate.
2.	Nara Institute of Science and Technology, Japan Shiga University, Banba, Japan	Green Drive	Green Drive is a route guidance system which is used to get shortest path. They used navigation system to enhance the overall control of the city. Dynamic route guidance method is used where k-shortest path algorithm is utilizing. In order to reduce traffic congestion formed by unequal traffic DRG is needed to distribute the traffic. Each road segment travel time is calculated by Green Drive and guides the vehicles in order to minimize the travel time for cars around the whole city.	This approach reduces average time by 10 to 60% as compared to other system.

3.	Nara Institute of Science and Technology, Japan Shiga University, Banba	Green Swirl	Traffic signal control method is used to give smooth flow of traffic through signals without any stop where Green Wave is formed. In this Green Swirl app manually swirls are designed according to the road network and city pattern. Vehicles can run at the lawful speed limit on a swirl without stopping unless there is traffic jam.	This approach reduces average time by 10 to 20% as compared to green wave.
4.	Sri Sairam Engineering college, India	Intelligent automatic traffic control for ambulance	It interlinks the ambulance and the traffic signals station using cloud network. It uses the functionality of RFID (radio frequency identification) to implement the ITS control.	Using RFID give accurate results in model as compared to camera. Proposed method better the performance of traffic light violation detection system but it is cost effective, so another technique must be used.
5.	SRM University, India	Dynamic traffic signal control algorithm	The proposed algorithm which is used to control the traffic congestion in emergency condition is as follows: Determine the queue length of traffic. Determine the presence of Emergency Vehicles as well as setting the priority of the present scenario (Best to worst). This algorithm also assigns the green light to the suitable path and calculates the green light duration for each phase.	This model is a success, to overcome traffic congestion when an emergency vehicle meets at the intersection point. But proposed algorithm needs to be more efficient as it take times (i.e. time complexity) to calculate the best scenario.
6.	Nagpur, Maharashtra, India	Survey paper for intelligent traffic control system.	It interlinks the ambulance and the traffic signals by using image processing techniques. As RFID has limited range and image processing has no range that's why they are using image processing. Image processing determined from where ambulance is approaching the signal will stop performing the normal operation.	This system is very efficient for ambulance to reach the destination on time without any delay in time. However, it reduces the traffic congestion and death trolls using simple image processing technique. But in bad weather conditions image processing will not perform its work as effectively as on sunny day.
7.	University of Pretoria, South Africa University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong, China	Distance based emergency vehicle dispatching algorithm	The proposed algorithm has the following steps: the sensor senses the presence of emergency vehicle and then calculates distance between EV's & intersection. The Controller check that is all EV's are at same distance if yes randomly choose direction set otherwise choose direction set in ascending order with the distance. Determine green light duration and send signal time to traffic light and verify passage of EV's at intersection and measure speed of EV's and count the vehicles moving along EV's towards next intersection and send measured data to next intersection. Controller check presence of EV's if no resumes normal operation otherwise repeat step from beginning	A visual sensor technique is applied effectively for sensing of emergency vehicle and resolves the issue of traffic congestion and set signal free for emergency vehicle. However, to outclass in all cases distance measurement in bad weather and complex traffic condition must be done

8.	Ayush Kr. Mittal and Deepika Bhandari Department of ECE Graphic Era University, Dehradun Uttarakhand, India	A Novel Approach to Implement Green Wave system and Detection of Stolen Vehicles	This system will detect a stolen vehicle that can use global positioning system or the functionality of RFID (radio frequency identification) both. The data relating to the vehicle has to be updated within the system info. It is an autonomous 2-tier system which will help in the Identification of emergency vehicles.	This system caters the problem of traffic clearance for emergency vehicle and stolen vehicles, when it passes from the traffic signal. The system is efficient for its approach and present satisfactory results in urban cities with a clear way without any traffic.
9.	K.L.N. College of Engineering, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India	Density Based Traffic Signal System	To overcome traffic jam in peak hours, a proposed method is developed which automate the signals on the basis of density measurement. Firstly, take an image of a road and perform the image processing and count the vehicle in the image and then check the density. Raspberry pi is used as a microcontroller which provides the signal timing based on the traffic density.	To perform better results and unnecessary waiting time during the signal, opencv software is used instead of matlab. As it is very cost effective, slow and not suitable in real time application. But however, there is still delay in time for others car standing opposite to crossing point. So more efficient system must be developed which minimize the time delay.
10.	Department of Computer Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Kurukshehra, India	Intelligent Traffic Management System for Prioritizing Emergency Vehicles in a Smart City	This system used traffic management server (TMS), vehicles, RSUs, sensors deployed at different locations, all interconnected with a VANET system. Finding the priority of the vehicle they can use Prioritizing Emergency Vehicle algorithm.	The proposed system eliminates the time delay for emergency vehicles and outperformed in terms of time constraints. But different priority levels for multiple scenarios (i.e. from all intersection point ambulance reach etc.) must be considered for better performance.

Table 3 Priorities

Our main focus is to cater the emergency condition in real time video streaming, so that without any delay, emergency vehicle (i.e. ambulance, fire brigade, and police cars) can cross the intersection point and reach their destination on time. We set the priority levels based on the urgency of the situation. The different type of vehicles and priorities on the basis of an incident are given in below *Table 3*. Fourth cases have been mentioned which show the urgency of situation.

In case 1, an ambulance is given the highest priority because a slight delay in traffic led to loss of human live, so our first priority is to give green wave route to ambulance whenever ambulance stuck in traffic signal. In case 2, if ambulance is not present on the traffic signals, fire brigade is given the highest priority. In case 3, police cars will be given the highest priority for situation like riots, thief's or crowd controlling situations. In case 4, normal users will be given least priority.

	Type of Vehicle	Priority Assigned	Signal timing
1.	Ambulance	First priority (Highest)	No timing until it passes through junction point.
2.	Fire brigade	Second priority	No timing until it passes through junction point.
3.	Police car	Third priority	No timing until it passes through junction point
4.	Normal user	Fourth Priority (Least)	Calculate on the basis of Density on each intersection point

V. CONCLUSION

A lot of research has been done for intelligent monitoring of traffic signal control system but an efficient solution for emergency vehicles (i.e. ambulance, fire brigade and police cars) as well as other vehicles yet needs to be sort out. An intelligent traffic control management system has been proposed to prioritize emergency vehicles in situations such as traffic congestion so that they don't get stuck in traffic and easily pass the intersection point when a sudden event happens in the city. The proposed research has solved the time delay for emergency vehicles as well as other vehicles at intersection point. However, we have also overcome the problem of traffic congestion on road in this proposed research with the use of traffic density measurement techniques on real time vehicle moving in simulation. Different levels of priorities are set for vehicles so that the one with high priority passes first and then the vehicles of the low priority would pass.

Control and manipulation of traffic signals have been discussed which work on the basis of traffic density calculated at intersection point. For better results, we have set two types of signal control, that is automatic signal and manual signal, which changes depending on the scenario of traffic at road. Automatic signal will work according to intensity of traffic density present on intersection point and on that basis, signal will open automatically where density is high but for the specific period of time and the density would not be updated till the next turn. Then the less dense lane signal would be open and so on. Equal density in each lane has also been discussed and solved effectively in which vehicles moving from left side will open first, then from back end, then from right side and then from front end. Similarly, different other scenarios have also been discussed to solve the problem of traffic jam. However, signal will operate manually when ambulance and other emergency vehicles are present on intersection point and other vehicles will wait until emergency vehicle passes (i.e. ambulance).

In the nutshell it is concluded that our approach has minimized the time delay and has outperformed others in terms of time constraints and traffic jam during peak hours. Our proposed method will play an important role in estimating time delay in traffic congestion, but it still requires development to attain higher accuracy. For future ideas, different priority levels for multiple incidents and scenarios need to be discussed.

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